

EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS OF GEOLOCATION DATA

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ABSTRACT

Geography and regional human behavior may be more fully comprehended via the study of geolocal data. A wealth of conveniences that make life easier in today's fast-paced, high-effort world. Many fields now rely heavily on geolocation and geographic information systems (GIS). Simply said, they may show geographical information and connect databases. This evaluates the effectiveness of an accommodation search in each given area as a way to demonstrate the value of geolocation. In this project, we apply K-Means Clustering to the geo-local data we gathered from the Foursquare API (Application Programming Interface) URL (Uniform Resource Locator) in order to classify accommodations and determine which ones are best suited to a given set of coordinates. In this work, we use feature selection to identify location indicator words (LIWs) and test whether a smaller feature set improves geolocation precision.

Keywords: Geolocation, GIS, LIW

1. INTRODUCTION

New possibilities are opening up as a result of the increased availability of geolocated data made possible by technological advancements and the proliferation of mobile devices and online social networks. The goal of exploratory data analysis is to get familiarity with the data in order to draw conclusions about its nature and significance. Graphical analysis and non-graphical analysis are the two main categories of EDA techniques. Analyzing data without preconceived conclusions is called exploratory data analysis. It often coincides with data cleansing. You may learn more about the dataset and start asking insightful questions with some practice.

No matter your perspective—academic, professional, or personal—geolocation and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) are helpful here for delving deeply into the vast amounts of data presently accessible in the "Big Data" age. To improve data analysis and presentation through maps, GIS is a potent tool for combining databases and geographic data. One of the reasons for the GIS's success is the ability to display data using maps, especially when dealing with multisource databases in a complicated process. Data collection and extraction from online sources are at the heart of exploratory analysis of geolocation data, which is then utilized to learn as much as possible about a certain region, market, lodging option, etc.

This is the kind of information that may be gotten from other places, like Google maps. In contrast, in exploratory analysis of geolocal data, we get to choose what kind of data we should be able to receive by not receiving all the undesired information, even if the procedure itself may be the same. As an illustration, we will perform data analysis to determine where and how many dormitories are located within a 2- to 5-kilometer radius, as well as the locations of any colleges, libraries, convenience stores, and other services that might be of use to students in the area.

1.2 Objective

- K-Means Clustering is used in this method to sort available housing in a city according to factors including the students' desired amenities, price range, and distance from campus.
- Displaying the findings of a field of interest to the user, determined by geolocation analysis, on a map of a certain region or city based on coordinates.

1.3 Scope

- The number of locations that can be evaluated with a single moule may be expanded.
- Our work may be used for various reasons, such as discovering regional and geographical differences in student choices.
- We could work on making the system multitask more effectively.
- Data analysis is time-consuming, especially when dealing with large amounts of data all at once. As a result, we may work to find a solution to this problem.
- Data collision occurs when many sets of data are processed simultaneously, making it difficult to differentiate between them. Which more advanced algorithms can solve.

1.4 Existing System

Location and GIS should encourage cutting-edge methods that account for geographical heterogeneity and spatial autocorrelation, from a theoretical standpoint. Such updated approaches to competition analysis in the accommodation sector may be more grounded in reality. In order to keep track of how fierce the rivalry is in a certain area, it is possible to crawl the Internet for geographical information using a section defines system.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

University of Melbourne, December 2012, Geolocation Prediction in Social Media Data Using Location-Indicative Words. [1] Massive amounts of user-generated content, such as tweets and status updates on Facebook, are created every day as social media platforms grow in popularity.1 The field of natural language processing now has a wealth of fresh information from which to learn and grow. Predicting the physical location of a message or person from their online activity is one such difficulty. In this work, we take a user's twitter stream as a whole to make a geolocation estimate down to the city level.

Points, grids, and population centers are all ways that geolocations may be recorded and organized (Wing and Baldrige, 2011; Roller et al., 2012; Cheng et al., 2010; Kinsella et al., 2011). A point-based representation is too fine-grained for our purpose and causes computational hurdles. In this concept, we combine neighbouring cities that fall under the jurisdiction of the same government.

The Massachusetts Institute of Technology Conducted an Exploratory Study of a Smartphone-Based Travel Survey:[2]. Singapore's Smartphone Travel Survey: An Exploratory Study. January 2015 is the 94th annual meeting of the Research Record. Recent developments in mobile sensing technologies and the extraordinary growth of smartphones have substantially increased the scope of available data on individual modes of transportation. Limited sample size, underreporting of total completed trips, and imprecision in stated trip start and finish timings (1) are common issues in traditional self-reported travel surveys. Detailed information for new agent and activity-based behavioral models may be gathered using smartphone-based questionnaires.

Twitter-based social media recommendation system developed by J. Kevin. J. Kevin unveiled a new method of exploratory analysis in August of this year.[3] which explain how to build a recommendation engine using Twitter, To begin, a model is built to anticipate user preferences by enhancing matrix factorization with personal and preference data from Yelp. However, an algorithm is being developed to analyze user posting behavior in order to determine a person's posting behavior vectors from their previous tweets and Yelp reviews.

Cyber Security Faculty of Information Science and Technology University of Malaysia Recommender System using Geolocated Clustering Empirical Research.[4] The Cyber Security Department of the University of Malaysia's Faculty of Information Science and Technology released it on December 12. Integrated CyberEvidence (ICE) is a Big Data tool created by Cyber Security Malaysia to sift through massive amounts of digital evidence. Coordinated Malware & Remediation Platform provides ICE with

malware cyber-intelligence enhanced data used in the recommendation system. The first step in developing a recommender system is to figure out what kind of application will be needed and how the data will be put to use.

IJARST released a paper on May 5, 2022, utilizing exploratory data analysis on geolocation data to create a system to recommend lodgings for newcomers. There has been a lot of migration going all around the globe, and much of it is students looking to get a better education in a different nation. Distance learning, in which students travel great distances to study with subject matter experts or to take advantage of better possibilities in the host nation, is one of the oldest forms of education. This is especially true for the many students who go to India, and from India to other nations, in search of better educational opportunities.

3. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

► **Hardware requirements**

- CPU/processor: Minimum dual core intel/AMD processor at 2Ghz
- RAM: 4GB minimum
- Storage: 500MB minimum
- Internet connection

► **Software requirements**

- Operating system: OS independent
- JYUPITER Compiler or VS code

4. DESIGN OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

METHODOLOGY

- Obtain data sets from appropriate repositories
- Clean the datasets to prepare them for analysis using Pandas.
- Get location information via the Foursquare API (REST APIs).
- Group the locations into groups using Scikit Learn's K-Means clustering
- Collect datasets from the appropriate areas;
- Display results on a map using Folium/Seaborn

Technologies and Algorithms

- Python
- K-Means Clustering
- Data Cleaning
- Data Preparation
- Rest API
- Data Visualization

MODULES

Fig 1: Modules in exploratory geolocational data analysis

- **Data Collection Module:** User information should be gathered and stored in a database for analysis.
- **Cleaning and visualizing Module:** Users enter their information and then utilize the system's data cleaning tools to ensure that only relevant information is stored in each of the system's many fields (such as title, distance, position, address, contacts, id, and location).
- **K-means clustering:** K-Means Clustering is used to identify the most convenient lodging options for students in every city.
- **Geolocational data:** The system will display all of the information gleaned from geolocational data, such as an individual's address, contact details, and coordinates.
- **Plotting Result on the map:** The system then plots all of the analytical findings it has obtained on a map and stores them in an HTML file.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

5.1 Tools used:

json: It's utilized while developing web-based or add-on-browser-based apps written in JavaScript. Structured data may be serialized into JSON and sent over a network.

- **Pandas as pd:** Pandas simplifies a wide variety of mundane but necessary data-related activities, including as:
 - Data cleaning
 - Data fill
 - Data normalization
 - Merges and joins
 - Data visualization
- **Requests:** Requests library can be used to **scrape the data from the website**.
- **Tabulate:** printing small tables without hassle: just one function call, formatting is guided by the data itself
- **Sklearn.cluster: Non-flat geometry clustering** is useful when the **clusters have a specific shape**, i.e., a non-flat manifold, and the standard Euclidean distance is not the right metric.
- **K-Means:** K-Means Clustering is an **Unsupervised Learning algorithm**, which groups the unlabeled dataset into different clusters.
- **Random:** A random library is used for **peptide sequence optimization**
- **Numpy as np:** Numpy is very useful in performing operations that are related to linear algebra and for its handling of random numbers.
- **Folium:** Folium is a Python library used for **visualizing geospatial data**

6. RESULTS

VISUALIZING THE DATASET

Fig 2: data visualization

In this section, we'll examine the dataset in question, visualize the data that will be applied, and then create a graph based on the visual representation of the data.

Determining clusters

Fig 3: Number of clusters

The graph in the associated depiction indicates how many possible clusters may be generated from the data, or how many times each cluster occurs in the data.

Fetching data form HERE API

	title	id	language	ontologyId	resultType	access	distance	categories	references	addressLabel
0	Government Nursing College	here:pds:place:356tends-d7a521068c4b48bfaf4a26...	en-GB	here:cm:ontology:university	place	[[{"lat": 17.31923, "lng": 76.83978}]]	140	[[{"id": "800-8200-0173", "name": "Higher Educa..."}]]	[[{"supplier": {"id": "core"}, "id": "105910329..."}]]	Government Nursing College, Shambhognlli, Kala...
1	D R S School of Institute	here:pds:place:356tends-2f2a702229bc4bc0b57d86...	en-GB	here:cm:ontology:university	place	[[{"lat": 17.31923, "lng": 76.83978}]]	140	[[{"id": "800-8200-0173", "name": "Higher Educa..."}]]	[[{"supplier": {"id": "core"}, "id": "105910331..."}]]	D R S School of Institute, Shambhognlli, Kalab...
2	Mahadeppa Rampur Medical College	here:pds:place:356tends-27a1e8553fd54c2da243cd...	en-GB	here:cm:ontology:university	place	[[{"lat": 17.31923, "lng": 76.83978}]]	140	[[{"id": "800-8200-0173", "name": "Higher Educa..."}]]	[[{"supplier": {"id": "core"}, "id": "105910331..."}]]	Mahadeppa Rampur Medical College, Shambhognlli...
3	Government Independent College	here:pds:place:356jx7ps-c9a2d1f44a9b01160cac0f...	en-GB	here:cm:ontology:university	place	[[{"lat": 17.31736, "lng": 76.83743}]]	441	[[{"id": "800-8200-0173", "name": "Higher Educa..."}]]	[[{"supplier": {"id": "core"}, "id": "111332973..."}]]	Government Independent College, Shambhognlli, ...
4	College of Teacher Education	here:pds:place:356jx7ps-cdd4ec32540f031a32e9cd...	en-GB	here:cm:ontology:university	place	[[{"lat": 17.3174, "lng": 76.83649}]]	494	[[{"id": "800-8200-0173", "name": "Higher Educa..."}]]	[[{"supplier": {"id": "core"}, "id": "111332978..."}]]	College of Teacher Education, Shambhognlli, Ka...
5	H. K. E Society M. S. I. Arts & Science Degree...	here:pds:place:356tends-aa0b196d52a04aa89bb107...	en-GB	here:cm:ontology:university	place	[[{"lat": 17.31584, "lng": 76.83718}]]	576	[[{"id": "800-8200-0173", "name": "Higher Educa..."}]]	[[{"supplier": {"id": "core"}, "id": "120862221..."}]]	H. K. E Society M. S. I. Arts & Science Degree...

Fig 4: Fetching data

Cleaning API data

	title	address.label	distance	access	position.lat	position.lng	address.postalCode
0	Government Nursing College	Government Nursing College, Shambhognlli, Kala...	140	[[{"lat": 17.31923, "lng": 76.83978}]]	17.31923	76.83978	585106
1	D R S School of Institute	D R S School of Institute, Shambhognlli, Kalab...	140	[[{"lat": 17.31923, "lng": 76.83978}]]	17.31923	76.83978	585106
2	Mahadeppe Rampur Medical College	Mahadeppe Rampur Medical College, Shambhognlli...	140	[[{"lat": 17.31923, "lng": 76.83978}]]	17.31923	76.83978	585106
3	Government Independent College	Government Independent College, Shambhognlli, ...	441	[[{"lat": 17.31736, "lng": 76.83743}]]	17.31720	76.83743	585106
4	College of Teacher Education	College of Teacher Education, Shambhognlli, Ka...	494	[[{"lat": 17.3174, "lng": 76.83649}]]	17.31730	76.83651	585106
5	H. K. E Society M. S. I. Arts & Science Degree...	H. K. E Society M. S. I. Arts & Science Degree...	576	[[{"lat": 17.31584, "lng": 76.83718}]]	17.31585	76.83733	585106
6	M. S. I. College	M. S. I. College, Shambhognlli, Kalaburagi 585...	590	[[{"lat": 17.31539, "lng": 76.83778}]]	17.31553	76.83777	585106
7	H K E Polytechnic College	H K E Polytechnic College, Shambhognlli, Kalab...	621	[[{"lat": 17.31538, "lng": 76.83778}]]	17.31523	76.83779	585106
8	Government Polytechnic	Government Polytechnic, Shambhognlli, Kalabura...	722	[[{"lat": 17.31675, "lng": 76.83438}]]	17.31673	76.83421	585106
9	Vijaya Vidyalaya Copm Pre Uni College	Vijaya Vidyalaya Copm Pre Uni College, Aiwan E...	722	[[{"lat": 17.32054, "lng": 76.83279}]]	17.32052	76.83295	585106
10	Pda College of Engineering	Pda College of Engineering, Shambhognlli, Kala...	808	[[{"lat": 17.31529, "lng": 76.83462}]]	17.31527	76.83445	585106
11	Kottal Basaveshwar Community College	Kottal Basaveshwar Community College, Aiwan E ...	814	[[{"lat": 17.31722, "lng": 76.83291}]]	17.31722	76.83289	585106
12	D R S School of Institute	D R S School of Institute, Rajapur, Kalaburagi...	816	[[{"lat": 17.32263, "lng": 76.8471}]]	17.32263	76.84710	585106

Fig 5: Cleaning API Data

When we get information from the HERE API, it will likely include details that the user isn't interested in seeing or that are irrelevant to their needs. The goal of "Cleaning the API data" is to get rid of the extraneous information users don't care about and instead provide just the most relevant details.

Counting Number of Department Colleges

	position.lat	position.lng	college
0	17.31923	76.83978	20
1	17.31923	76.83978	20
2	17.31923	76.83978	20
3	17.31720	76.83743	20
4	17.31730	76.83651	20
5	17.31585	76.83733	20
6	17.31553	76.83777	20
7	17.31523	76.83779	20
8	17.31673	76.83421	20
9	17.32052	76.83295	20
10	17.31527	76.83445	20
11	17.31722	76.83289	20
12	17.32263	76.84710	20
13	17.31609	76.83312	20
14	17.31514	76.83393	20
15	17.32841	76.83889	20
16	17.32780	76.83606	20
17	17.32228	76.84817	20
18	17.32718	76.84490	20
19	17.31553	76.83266	20

Fig 6: Counting Departments

The information is shown here, together with the latitude and longitude coordinates of the determined locations.

Run K-means clustering on Data-frame

Here we obtain the coordinates of the place as well as how many facilities are available in that region.

```
#Run K-means clustering on dataframe
kclusters = 1

kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=kclusters, random_state=0).fit(df_final)
df_final['Cluster']=kmeans.labels_
df_final['Cluster']=df_final['Cluster'].apply(str)
df_final
```

✓ 0.1s

Figure 7: Obtaining Coordinates

Plotting Clustered Locations on Map Using Folium

Fig 8: Final result showing all location on the map

Saving Map:

Finally we save the map in the form of HTML file.

```
#saving the map
map_bom.save("map/college.html")
```

✓ 0.8s

Fig 9: Saving Map

7. CONCLUSION

This study aims to explore the utilization of geolocation technology in facilitating student accommodation within a specific geographic region. The research will employ geo locational data analysis to identify the fundamental requirements of students, such as the proximity of educational institutions, libraries, hostels, and bookstores. The present study aims to conduct an analysis that offers comprehensive and precise insights into the various areas or zones encompassed within a given range.

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